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Letter to the medical community

Therapy of rare diseases at the intersection of culture, regulation, and clinical practice in Europe and the United States

Dear Colleagues,

Healthcare systems differ significantly across nations due to cultural, regulatory, and systemic determinants. A paramount distinction lies in the latitude afforded to medical practitioners concerning their treatment protocols, especially when conventional therapies fall short. Having practiced for many years in Eastern Europe, I had always assumed the concept of “therapeutic freedom”, or as the Germans call it “Therapiefreiheit”, as a given.

However, during my preparations for a new professional position with an international network practice illuminated the constraints present in the Anglo-Saxon world, notably the United States. In the majority of European nations, “therapeutic freedom” empowers physicians with the discretion to adapt treatments to the singular needs of patients, with whatever I believe helps - after informed consent. The principle of therapeutic freedom refers to a foundational tenet in medical treatment, whereby, based on a physician's professional expertise, they inherently possess

the discretion to select the treatment modality they deem appropriate to recommend to the patient. In essence, the healthcare provider has considerable latitude in choosing the therapy that they perceive as medically necessary. However, they are obligated to align their decisions with the prevailing scientific knowledge and exercise due diligence. Such autonomy is invaluable, and at times, lifesaving for those treating rare or intricate medical conditions, granting an enhanced degree of personalization in treatment strategies. This autonomy operates within the ethical bounds of ensuring patient consent and adhering to the principle of “do no harm.”

When conventional treatments are missing or prove inadequate, physicians in many European countries can resort to what is, again in Germany (a nation with a idiosyncratic medical culture) called “individueller Therapievversuch.” This approach, deeply rooted in the nation often considered the birthplace of therapeutic freedom, enables healthcare providers to pursue extensive and innovative off-label treatments, with the patient's informed consent, devoid of legal consequences. Such practices are an integrated part of medical care in the EU.

Another aspect I had taken for granted as a European physician is the synergistic relationship between doctors and pharmacists. Pharmacies in numerous EU nations are not just dispensaries; they possess the expertise to compound medications tailored to individual patient requirements. This interdisciplinary collaboration enriches the healthcare landscape with far reaching consequences, facilitating instantaneous amendments to treatment plans.

Contrastingly, the healthcare paradigm in the United States is characterized by stringent regulations surrounding tailor-made or off-label treatments, often negatively labeled as “experimental”. The closest U.S. counterpart might be “compassionate use” or “expanded access,” but these avenues are ridiculously heavily regulated. U.S. physicians grapple with intricate regulatory hurdles, including institutional review boards and liability issues, which curtail their ability to provide personalized treatments. It’s challenging to envision treating over 90% of my rare disease patients within such constraints. Furthermore, the health systems in the European Union are well grounded in communitarian principles, emphasizing personal relationships, mutual trust, and loyalty over mere transactions. This cultural foundation creates an environment where medical practitioners can voice uncertainties without fearing professional backlash, promoting a collaborative and patient-centric approach to healthcare. To truly value the significance of “Therapiefreiheit” and “individueller Therapieversuch,” consider a patient diagnosed with an unnamed syndrome causing autonomic dysfunctions and severe hypersympathotonia. All standard interventions had been ineffective, necessitating a novel approach. An interdisciplinary team, led by clinician and pharmaceutical expert Ali Asgari, devised a highly potent combination of Tramadol, Midazolam, Procaine, Alprazolam, and Dimetindene (Amitradicaine formula).

Administered intramuscularly with informed consent, this concoction was optimized for both safety and efficacy. Collaborations with cardiologists were essential, especially since the patient exhibited a Left Bundle Branch Block (LBBB), ensuring no cardiac complications. Continuous monitoring revealed no adverse cardiac outcomes, such as variations in the QRS complex or QTc interval. This tailored treatment remarkably improved the patient’s condition, resolving severe gastroparesis, painful motility issues and dozens other symptoms, exemplifying the depth of customization possible under the European medical framework. While no healthcare system is flawless, many European countries provide a blend of regulatory flexibility and collaboration opportunities for physicians addressing complex and rare medical conditions. This adaptability starkly

contrasts with the U.S.’s over-regulated, liability-conscious environment, posing both opportunities and challenges for personalized patient care.

Conclusion

I regard all physicians licensed to practice medicine in continental Europe as distinctly privileged.

Conflicts of interest

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